

INTERNAL EFFICIENCY OF THE INTEGRATED TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME (ITEP): A STUDY OF STUDENT SUCCESS AND INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS IN PUNJAB, INDIA

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of Internal Efficiency on the success in developing human capital among students enrolled in the Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) in Punjab, India. A descriptive correlation mixed-methods design was adopted. The data were collected using structured questionnaires and interviews from three public universities in Punjab that implement ITEP. EFA confirmed the validity and reliability of the measurement scales. Results from the Pearson Correlation Coefficient revealed that institutional inputs ($r = 0.470$, $p < 0.01$), teaching practices ($r = 0.370$, $p < 0.01$), and administrative processes ($r = 0.431$, $p < 0.01$) were significantly correlated to the success of students and human capital development. Multiple regression analysis revealed that the combined institutional inputs, teaching practices, and administrative processes accounted for 28.8% of the variance in student success and human capital outcomes ($R^2 = 0.288$, $p < 0.001$). However, institutional inputs and administrative processes emerged as significant predictors, while teaching practices did not have a statistically significant independent effect. The findings show that the internal efficiency of ITEP is significantly shaped by the quality of institutional resources and administrative systems, which in turn improve the preparedness of the students, their employability, and professional competence. The study concludes that strengthening institutional infrastructure and administrative governance is crucial for maximizing the contribution of ITEP to enhance the educational human capital of students in Punjab, India. It was therefore recommended that HEIs in Punjab offering ITEP prioritize strengthening institutional inputs while also improving administrative efficiency.

Key Words: *Internal Efficiency, Institutional Inputs, Administrative Process, Student Success.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, private and public levels have continuously invested in activities promoting human capital development [1]. Over the years, both at private and public levels worldwide have continuously invested in activities that can promote human capital development. The education system includes internal efficiency and the optimal use of resources to produce graduates with minimal wastage [2]. Education is a foundation of national development in India, and therefore, improving the internal efficiency of teacher education has been identified as a critical priority [3]. This urgency is highlighted by the introduction of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in some public universities in India. Among the central reforms is introducing the Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) by the National Council for Teacher Education [4], [5].

While implementing this reform is ongoing in Punjab, vital questions arise regarding the internal efficiency of the ITEP programme. In particular, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the students' ability to transform educational inputs into successful student outcomes with minimal resource wastage. This gap is particularly salient at the state level, such as in Punjab, where there exist socio-economic disparities, variation in capacity of the institutions, coupled with existing challenges in higher education, and above all, the under-enrollment and uneven infrastructure can adversely affect student retention and completion [6]. Financial, academic, and gender-based barriers threaten internal efficiency of the ITEP programme [7], [8].

While the ITEP in India represents a significant policy shift to resolve long-standing fragmentation issues and inadequate practical training in Indian teacher education, its success is not guaranteed. The strategic intention to create a high quality, holistic teaching cadre through an integrated curriculum may be undermined by institutional inefficiencies[9]. A systematic investigation into the internal efficiency of ITEP is therefore imperative to determine whether the objectives of the policy are being realized or not. If the inefficiencies in academics, infrastructures, gender based differences, are not addressed, these inefficiencies risk undermining the anticipated improvements in teacher quality and national educational progress in India. The Internal Efficiency concept frames this research to evaluate the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) in Punjab. While both academic and administrative factors potentially influence the performance and success of students, their relative contributions in the ITEP context remain unclear. This study therefore seeks to determine the impact of teaching/learning processes, and to assess the institutional inputs that influence the internal efficiency of ITEP in Punjab, as well as to assess the effect of administrative processes on student success. The study examined the relationship between institutional inputs and key output/outcome indicators. By doing so, it aimed to assess the program's contribution to developing certified teachers and building the country's educational human capital.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Human Capital Theory.

This study is founded on the Human Capital Theory of [10] and [1] which states that education is an investment yielding returns through enhanced productivity. This study posits that inefficiencies within ITEP institutions diminish the return on this national investment.

Scope of the study

2.2. Empirical Literature Review.

The ability of institutions to maximize resources in order to produce qualified graduates with the least amount of waste in terms of dropout, repetition, and delayed completion is referred to as internal efficiency in teacher education [11]. The timely completion of the program demonstrates internal efficiency within the context of the Integrated Teacher Education Programme, providing real-world learning opportunities and training for professionally qualified teachers who can make valuable contributions to the educational system [12].

Institutional inputs, including infrastructure, governance structures, faculty caliber, curriculum coherence, and admissions selectivity, have a significant impact on internal efficiency in teacher education institutions. According to a study by [13] teacher competence and institutional efficiency are influenced by several factors, including selectivity, the integration of theory and practice, pedagogical quality, and the professional disposition of teacher educators. Furthermore, [14] highlights that institutions with superior faculty, stronger curricula, and sufficient learning tools exhibit higher student retention and completion rates. The effectiveness of teacher education programs in various Indian states is influenced by variations in institutional funding and infrastructure [15].

Student achievement in ITEP institutions is further mediated by administrative, instructional, and learning procedures [16], [17]. Reflective teaching, mentorship, and formative assessment are examples of effective educational techniques that improve student involvement and advancement [18]. According to [19], student results are improved when teaching, learning, and institutional structures are strongly aligned. On the other hand, complex administrative processes, inflexible evaluation systems, and a lack of academic assistance all lead to student attrition and delayed completion [20]. Institutional models that prioritize equality, support, and transparency, such as the TEAMS Model, have been shown to boost student engagement and retention by demonstrating governance and encouraging policy innovation [21], [22].

The development of human capital in ITEP is significantly impacted by internal efficiency. Long-term academic achievements and school quality are directly impacted by effective teacher education systems, which guarantee the timely supply of trained teachers [23]. According to [11], education systems with higher internal efficiency reduce resource waste and increase graduate production, resulting in higher returns on investment. The 4-year ITEP is positioned as a strategic intervention to enhance human capital formation and increase teacher quality in the context of Indian reform [15]. Despite extensive literature on teacher education efficiency, empirical studies focusing on the internal efficiency of ITEP institutions at the regional level, particularly in Punjab, remain limited. Moreover, few studies explicitly link institutional and process-related efficiency to human capital outcomes. Addressing this gap, the present study examines the institutional inputs, teaching and learning process, and administrative processes that influence internal efficiency in ITEP institutions in Punjab.

2.3. Conceptual Framework.

The concept of Internal Efficiency frames the study within an educational system. The study examined the relationship between institutional inputs and key output/outcome indicators. The primary efficiency indicators were student success, retention, and timely graduation rates. Efficiency is also conceptualized regarding the program's contribution to developing qualified, competent, and certified teachers, thereby building Punjab's educational human capital. The analytical framework for this study is **Internal Efficiency**, a concept concerned with the relationship between inputs (e.g., institutional resources, student intake) and educational outputs/outcomes within a system [24], [25], [26]. In this context, efficiency is operationalized through student success rates, retention rates, and timely graduation rates. Furthermore, we extend the concept to consider the outcome of teacher education: the development of qualified, competent, and certified teachers as a critical investment in Punjab's educational human capital.

2.4. Specific Objectives of the Study.

- i. To assess the institutional inputs that influences the internal efficiency of ITEP in Punjab.
- ii. To evaluate the effect of teaching/learning processes on student success within ITEP institutions in Punjab.
- iii. To examine the influence of administrative processes on student success in ITEP institutions of Punjab.
- iv. To analyze how internal efficiency in ITEP contributes to human capital outcomes in Punjab

2.5. Research Questions.

1. What institutional inputs significantly influence the internal efficiency of the ITEP in Punjab?
2. How do teaching/learning affect student success within ITEP in Punjab?
3. To what extent do administrative policies affect student success within ITEP in Punjab?
4. How does internal efficiency in ITEP translate into improved human capital outcomes in Punjab?

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Study Design, Population, and Data Collection.

This study employed a descriptive correlational research design utilizing a mixed-methods approach [27]. The study was conducted at three universities approved by the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) to offer the ITEP in Punjab, India, which include included; the Central University of Punjab (Bathinda), Guru Nanak Dev University (Amritsar), and Punjabi University (Patiala). These public universities were purposively selected as they had admitted at least one complete cohort of ITEP students was a necessary condition for analyzing student progression and graduation rates [28], [29]. The study population included teacher trainees enrolled in ITEP, faculty members, and administrators from these universities. A stratified sample of approximately 100 participants was drawn, comprising 80 students and 20 faculty/administrators. Concurrently, semi-structured interviews were conducted with faculty, administrators, and students to gain contextual insights into institutional management, challenges in curriculum implementation, and perceptions of efficiency [30].

3.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis and Reliability.

This study operationalized three key variables: the three constitutive dimensions of **Internal Efficiency**, the dependent variable of **Student Success, and Institutional Factors**. The construct of **Internal Efficiency** was measured in terms of **Institutional inputs**, teaching-learning and administrative and internal efficiency using 25 items developed and tested for validity and reliability. The 30-item scale was initially assessed and refined through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), resulting in a final 25-item instrument, which was captured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Table 1: Threshold for Factor Analysis and Reliability

Factor analysis	Threshold value
1. Factor loading	≥ 0.60 Or 0.70
2. KMO	> 0.50
3. Eigen value	> 1
4. Cumulative %	≥ 0.60 or 0.70
Reliability test	
1. Cronbach's Alpha	≥ 0.60 or 0.70
2. Item- total correlation	≥ 0.50

Source: Shrestha (2021).

3.3. Measurement.

3.3.1. Psychometric properties of the internal efficiency scale.

In Table 2, a KMO value greater than 0.60 establishes item validity, confirming that each item was appropriate for scale retention [32]. A singular factor structure (Eigenvalue = 2.24) accounting for 57% of the total variation was found by

factor analysis applying principal component analysis with Varimax rotation. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy of 0.70 indicated acceptable sample adequacy for factor analysis. The recommended threshold of 0.50 was exceeded by all factor loadings, which varied from 0.53 to 0.86 [33], [34]. With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70, the scale's internal consistency was accepted as adequate. Due to its high factor loading and conceptual significance to the institutional factor measurement construct, item IN1 was retained, despite displaying an unusual pattern of correlations. According to [35], this finding confirms the homogeneity of the scale items, as it matches the commonly used reliability criterion of 0.70. All of these findings support the validity and reliability of the research variables used in this study.

Table 2: Factor Analysis and Reliability of Internal Efficiency Construct

Component	Exploratory Factor analysis				Reliability	
	FL (Rotated Component Matrix ^a)	Overall KMO	Eigenvalue	CU%	ITC	α
IN1	0.86	0.70	2.24	57	0.25	0.70
IN2	0.74				0.46	
IN3	0.80				0.42	
IN4	0.53				0.35	
IN5	0.71				0.40	
IN6	0.74				0.44	

Note: FL = Factor Loading score, MSA = Measures of Sampling Adequacy, KMO = Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy, Eig. = Eigen value, CU% = Cumulative %, ITC = Item- total correlation, α = Cronbach Alpha.

3.3.2. Psychometric properties of the teaching practice.

In Table 3, EFA was conducted to validate the scale used for measuring the teaching of ITEP students in their institutions. The Factor analysis of the 5-item Teaching Practice scale yielded a single-factor solution (Eigenvalue = 2.69), explaining 54% of the variance, with satisfactory sampling adequacy (KMO = 0.80). From the findings, all items of the teaching and learning constructs demonstrated acceptable to excellent factor loadings (ranging from 0.61 to 0.81) and adequate item-total correlations (ranging from 0.44 to 0.64). The scale showed good internal consistency reliability ($\alpha = 0.78$), supporting its use in this study.

Table 3: Factor Analysis and Reliability of Teaching/Learning Construct

Component	Exploratory Factor analysis				Reliability	
	FL	Overall KMO	Eigenvalue	CU%	ITC	α
TP1	0.752	0.80	2.693	54	0.578	0.78
TP2	0.789				0.624	
TP3	0.807				0.643	
TP4	0.613				0.440	
TP5	0.692				0.519	

3.3.3. Psychometric properties of the administrative processes.

The Administrative Processes scale showed outstanding psychometric qualities. With a sufficient KMO of 0.80 and a good Eigenvalue (3.27) that explained 54.53% of the variance, factor analysis demonstrated robust sampling sufficiency. Every item had strong internal consistency reliability ($\alpha = 0.82$) and loaded nicely on the factor (varying from 0.54 to 0.84). The scale's usage as an essential measure of institutional administrative efficiency is supported by its good psychometric qualities.

Table 4: Factor Analysis and Reliability of Administrative Processes Construct

Component	Exploratory Factor analysis				Reliability	
	FL	Overall KMO	Eigenvalue	CU%	ITC	α
AP1	0.790	0.80	3.272	54.533	0.659	0.82
AP2	0.538				0.421	
AP3	0.636				0.486	
AP4	0.811				0.664	
AP5	0.836				0.703	
AP6	0.773				0.647	

4. FINDINGS

Data analysis was done using SPSS, in which descriptive statistics summarized institutional and student data. Inferential statistics (correlation and multiple regressions) tested relationships among institutional factors and student success indicators of ITEP. At the same time, hypotheses were tested at a **0.05 significance level**. Qualitative data from interviews were analyzed thematically using manual coding to identify emergent themes. The findings from both datasets were then triangulated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the contextual factors affecting internal efficiency.

4.1. Demographic information.

Table 4 presents the demographic characteristics of ITEP students and stakeholders, with a focus on gender and age distribution. The results show that female respondents (64.3%) outnumbered male respondents (35.7%), indicating that the ITEP program has a greater female participation rate. The age-related data indicate that a majority of respondents (56.0%) are below 20 years old, followed by 32.1% aged 20–30 years. Only 4.8% and 7.1% of the faculty members, respectively, fall within the 30–40 and 40 and above categories. This distribution reveals that most participants are pre-service teachers enrolled in initial teacher education.

Table 4: Demographic Information

S/No.	Category	F	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Male	30	35.7%
	Female	54	64.3%
	Total	84	100%
2	Age		
	Below 20	47	56.0
	20 - 30	27	32.1
	30 - 40	4	4.8
	40 and above	6	7.1
	Total	84	100%
	Year 1	33	39.3
	Year 2	51	60.7
	Total	84	100.0

4.2. Institutional inputs.

Student opinions of institutional inputs are shown in Table 5. With 66.7% of students thinking that ICT facilities were adequate, they obtained the highest rating ($M = 3.68$, $SD = 1.00$). Good scores were also given to physical learning areas ($M = 3.55$). However, there was space for improvement in the areas of teaching practice opportunities ($M = 3.39$) and library resources ($M = 3.39$), with 22.6% and 23.8% of respondents disagreeing, respectively. These results suggest that, although the physical and technological infrastructure is sufficient, academic resources and experiential aspects of learning may need to be strengthened to achieve better student outcomes and ITEP success in Punjab, India.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for Institutional Inputs

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SD	M	STD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
1. Classrooms and teaching spaces are adequate for our classes.	3 (3.6)	11 (13.1)	17 (20.2)	43 (51.2)	10 (11.9)	3.55	.99
2. Teaching and learning resources (textbooks, lab materials) are readily available.	5 (6)	8 (9.5)	23 (27.4)	35 (41.7)	13 (15.5)	3.51	1.06
3. The institution provides sufficient ICT for learning.	3 (3.6)	8 (9.5)	17 (20.2)	41 (48.8)	15 (17.9)	3.68	1.00
4. Library resources meet my course requirements.	6 (7.1)	14 (16.7)	14 (16.7)	41 (48.8)	9 (10.7)	3.39	1.11
5. There is regular access to teaching practice/school placement opportunities.	00 (00)	19 (22.6)	21 (25.0)	36 (42.9)	8 (9.5)	3.39	.94

SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree, M = Mean, STD = Standard Deviation.

The findings of this study show that institutional inputs such as classrooms, ICT, and learning resources moderately influence the academic experiences of students within ITEP, which concurs with Human Capital Theory [1], [10], which states that investment in educational infrastructure enhances learning efficiency and productivity.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics for Teaching practices & assessment

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SD	M	STD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
1. Innovative pedagogies are being employed by teachers.	1 (1.2)	6 (7.1)	14 (16.7)	50 (59.5)	13 (15.5)	3.81	.83
2. Teachers use varied teaching methods (lectures, group work, and practical).	3 (3.6)	5 (6.0)	12 (14.3)	45 (53.6)	19 (22.6)	3.86	.96
3. Courses are well organized, and learning outcomes are clear.	4 (4.8)	7 (8.3)	18 (21.4)	44 (52.4)	11 (13.1)	3.61	.98
4. Feedback on the assignment, is timely provided for improvement	1 (1.2)	8 (9.5)	13 (15.5)	50 (59.5)	12 (14.3)	3.76	.86
5. Practical sessions/simulations are linked to theory.	3 (3.6)	7 (8.3)	21 (25)	43 (51.2)	10 (11.9)	3.60	.93

SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree, M = Mean, STD = Standard Deviation.

Findings in Table 6 indicate that teaching practices and assessment strategies within ITEP are generally effective and positively perceived by students. The majority (76.2%) of respondents agreed that teachers employ innovative pedagogies ($M = 3.81$, $SD = .828$) and use varied teaching methods, such as lectures, group work, and practical sessions, represented by 75% ($M = 3.86$, $SD = .959$), reflecting active and diversified instructional approaches that enhance engagement. Similarly, timely feedback was indicated by 73.8% ($M = 3.76$, $SD = .859$) of respondents, and clear course organization by 65.5% ($M = 3.61$, $SD = .982$) of respondents, which suggests that there exist structured and supportive learning environments that facilitate continuous improvement. However, the relatively lower mean for linking practical sessions to theory shows 63.1% ($M = 3.60$, $SD = .933$), indicating the need for stronger integration between conceptual knowledge and practices for ITEP students to learn hands-on.

Table 7: Descriptive statistics for Administrative Processes & Services

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SD	M	STD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
1. Admission and registration processes are efficient and transparent.	3 (3.6)	2 (2.4)	14 (16.7)	49 (58.3)	16 (19.0)	3.87	.88
2. Academic counseling and guidance services are accessible.	2 (2.4)	6 (7.1)	14 (16.7)	50 (59.5)	12 (14.3)	3.76	.87
3. Timetabling is done fairly and published on time.	1 (1.2)	3 (3.6)	16 (19)	39 (46.4)	25 (29.8)	4.00	.86
4. Staff-student communication is effective.	2 (2.4)	3 (3.6)	14 (16.7)	49 (58.3)	16 (19.0)	3.88	.84
5. Student records and results are managed accurately.	1 (1.2)	1 (1.2)	9 (10.7)	50 (63.1)	20 (23.8)	4.07	.71
6. Campus security and welfare services meet diverse needs of student.	5 (6.0)	4 (4.8)	13 (15.5)	49 (58.3)	13 (15.5)	3.73	.99

SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree, M = Mean, STD = Standard Deviation.

Administrative processes and services within ITEP institutions are generally effective (Table 7). Respondents strongly agreed that student records and results are accurately managed, represented by 86.9% agreement ($M = 4.07$, $SD = 0.708$), and that timetabling is fair and timely, with 76.2% agreement ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.864$). Similarly, staff-student communication 77.3% ($M = 3.88$, $.842$), admission and registration processes (77.3%) ($M = 3.87$, 0.875) were rated

positively, reflecting efficient administrative coordination. Access to academic counseling and guidance services, 73.8% agreement ($M = 3.76$, $SD = .873$), and satisfaction with campus security and welfare, 73.8% agreement ($M = 3.73$, $SD = .986$), were also above average but comparatively lower, suggesting room for improvement in student support services.

Table 8: Descriptive statistics for Student Success & Human Capital Outcome

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SD	M	STD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
1. Students are well prepared for the teaching profession after this program.	00 (00)	1 (1.2)	17 (20.0)	47 (56)	19 (22.6)	4.00	.69
2. Academic performance (GPA) reflects the program's teaching quality.	00 (00)	6 (7.1)	18 (21.4)	51 (60.7)	9 (10.7)	3.75	.74
3. Decision-making processes in the institution are transparent.	1 (1.2)	5 (6.0)	22 (26.2)	42 (50.0)	14 (16.7)	3.75	.85
4. Students have developed subject specific pedagogy skills required for schools.	2 (2.4)	3 (3.6)	33 (39.3)	37 (34)	9 (10.7)	3.75	.83
5. There is a clear policy for promotions, appraisals, and workload.	1 (1.2)	2 (2.4)	28 (33.3)	46 (54.8)	7 (8.3)	3.67	.72
6. I participate in extracurricular /professional activities that improve employability	00 (00)	8 (9.5)	22 (26.2)	43 (51.2)	11 (13.1)	3.68	.82
7. The program helped students in the development of soft skills (communication, ICT).	00 (00)	4 (4.8)	22 (26.2)	47 (56.0)	11 (13.1)	3.77	.73
8. ITEP contributes to human capital development of students.	2 (2.4)	4 (4.8)	19 (22.6)	51 (60.7)	8 (9.5)	3.70	.80

SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree, M = Mean, STD = Standard Deviation.

Table 8 presents respondents' views on student success and human capital outcomes in the ITEP program. Overall, the mean scores ($M = 3.67$ – 4.00) indicate positive perceptions across all items. Most respondents agreed that students are well-prepared for the teaching profession, showing 78.6% agreement ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.694$), and that academic performance reflects the quality of teaching, with 71.4% agreement ($M = 3.75$, $SD = 0.742$). High ratings for soft skills development (69.1% agreement, $M = 3.77$, $SD = 0.734$) and professional participation (64.3% agreement, $M = 3.68$, $SD = 0.824$) clearly indicate that ITEP enhances employability and overall growth of students.

4.3. Correlation matrix.

The correlation analysis between Institutional inputs (IN) was moderately with students' success and outcomes (SSO) ($r = .470$, $p < .01$), showing that the availability and adequacy of institutional resources contribute to improved student performance (see Table 9). Teaching practices and assessment (TP) also showed a positive correlation with SSO ($r = .370$, $p < .01$), suggesting that effective instructional and evaluation methods enhance learner achievement. Similarly, administrative processes and services (APS) significantly correlated with SSO ($r = .431$, $p < .01$), implying that efficient institutional management positively influences academic experiences of students.

Table 9: Correlation analysis for factors of internal efficiency and students outcomes

		Student success & human capital outcome	Institutional inputs	Student success & human capital outcome	Administrative processes & services
Student success & human capital outcome	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	84			
Institutional inputs	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	84	84		
Teaching practices & assessment	Pearson Correlation	.370**	.559**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		
	N	84	84	84	
Administrative processes & services	Pearson Correlation	.431**	.427**	.497**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	84	84	84	84

Note: p -value < 0.05, 0.01

4.4. Regression analysis.

Table 10: Multiple linear regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.536 ^a	.288	.261	3.310	.288	10.762	3	80	.000	2.181

a. Predictors: (Constant), Institutional inputs, Teaching practices & assessment and administrative processes & services

b. Dependent Variable: Student success & human capital outcome

Table 10 shows that institutional inputs, teaching practices, assessment, and administrative processes and services jointly predict student success and human capital outcomes with a moderate positive relationship ($R = .536$). The model explains approximately 28.8% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.288$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.261$), indicating that institutional factors significantly lead to the development of students. The finding is consistent with HCT [1], [10] and studies [36], [37], [38], [39], [40], [41], whose findings point to the investment in teacher education inputs and processes to foster the acquisition of skills and competencies essential for human capital development and educational effectiveness.

Table 11: ANOVA Table for multiple regression linear model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	353.668	3	117.889	10.762	0.000 ^b
	Residual	876.367	80	10.955		
	Total					

a. Dependent Variable: Student success & human capital outcome

b. Predictors: (Constant), Institutional inputs, Teaching practices & assessment and administrative processes & services

Table 11 tests whether the regression model, which uses three predictors to explain "Student success & human capital outcome," for ITEP students, is statistically significant. The key finding is that the model is an essential predictor of the outcome variable. In other words, combining the three predictors better explains the variation in student success than a model with no predictors at all. This analysis reveals that a model combining Institutional inputs, Teaching practices & assessment, and Administrative processes & services is a statistically significant predictor of Student success & human capital outcome ($F(3, 80) = 10.76, p < .001$).

Table 12: Multiple regression coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	15.55	2.62		5.95	.000		
	IN	.330	.118	.326	2.80	.006	.658	.658
	TP	.066	.139	.057	.47	.638	.606	.606
	APS	.269	.114	.263	2.36	.020	.721	.721
a) Dependent Variable: Student success & human capital outcome								

Note: Significant at p -value $< 0.05, 0.01, \text{ and } 0.001$

Table 12 presents the regression coefficients, which show the individual contributions of institutional inputs (IN), teaching practices and assessment (TP), and administrative processes and services (APS) to student success and human capital outcomes. The institutional inputs ($\beta = 0.326, p = 0.006$) and administrative processes and services ($\beta = 0.263, p = 0.020$) are significant positive predictors, indicating that improvements in these factors enhance the success of student and human capital development. While teaching practices and assessment ($\beta = 0.057, t = 0.472, p = 0.638$) showed no significant effect, their isolated impact may be limited without strong institutional and administrative support.

4.5. Qualitative findings.

Participants emphasized the need for a more flexible and creativity-based curriculum to foster innovation within the ITEP. One student noted the importance of "more experiential and research-based learning" alongside "availability of material for practical programs" (R3). Additionally, participants recommended that greater attention be given to individual presentations to build confidence and professional identity (R5), with one participant stating that such opportunities would help children "consider themselves as future teachers" (R2). Another key suggestion was that "practical subjects need to be studied well" (R6), indicating a perceived gap between theoretical instruction and hands-on application in the current curriculum.

In my analysis of student perspectives, I identified a strong preference for experiential and observational learning facilitated by expert faculty. One participant (R7) articulated this clearly: "The teachers who teach us should be well-experienced and qualified because we learn faster by watching than by reading." The same participant connected this need to structural resources, adding, "More classes are needed for a better study experience, and secondly, more teachers are required to pay close attention to students from different majors."

Similarly,

We believe all three core science subjects such as Physics, Chemistry, and Biology should be offered. If that is not possible, at least a major and minor subject combination should be available, but right now, we are stuck with only one subject. Additionally, classroom assignments, such as term papers and PowerPoint presentations, often feel like a waste of time. Class tests should replace these (R16).

Another Respondent (R28) added the need to have more changes for ITEP. Stating, "The two institutional changes that would improve your learning.....there is limited number of faculties in our department....so there are no other options to us which can easily for our educational curriculum.....". while another participant added "Two institutional changes that would most improve my learning are (1) more interactive teaching methods and (2) better access to learning resources" (R42).

Participants proposed specific improvements to the teaching and support structures. One student suggested: "Our major teaching facility can be improved. A day should be dedicated for doubt clearing session; one day one subject. Details about the Scholarship should be discussed in class. Practice materials for non-core subjects should be provided" (R62).

In synthesizing this feedback, I observed that student suggestions centered on enhancing academic clarity, improving institutional communication, and providing resources to support learning. Still on teaching, participant student put these suggestions, "Our major teaching facility can be improved. A day should be dedicated for doubt clearing session; one day one subject. Details about Scholarship should be discussed in class. Practice materials for non core subjects should be provided" (R62).

Similarly one respondent pointed the need to expose students to field work.

Teachers are supportive, yet more regular feedback and mentoring sessions would further enhance learning. Regarding the ITEP program outcomes, the course provides a strong foundation in educational theory and pedagogy. However, incorporating more field-based experiences, skill-oriented workshops, and digital learning tools would better prepare us for real classroom challenges (R43).

The participant expressed a strong desire for applied, contextual learning, stating:

Our major subject, which is maths, mostly talks about the theoretical part only, but we are not taught practical applications in nature and for society. Teaching is always done in classrooms, which is not good. Teaching must also take place in nature so we can see, learn, and apply the theory (R40).

Participants explicitly linked physical infrastructure and safety provisions to their well-being and academic engagement. One student stated: "I propose making a combined study building near the hostel accessible 24/7 with a good Wi-Fi system. Going to the library alone at night and returning alone late at night over such a long distance is stressful in regard to safety concerns" (R13). This indicates the importance of late-night study and also points to the risks associated with solitary movement across campus after dark.

A critical theme of hygiene and health emerged, with students pointing to health consequences linked to inadequate infrastructure maintenance. One participant shared:

We need good facilities and clean washrooms in the hostel and academy. The washroom should be cleaned once every two hours. I have faced bad health many times in this university due to urinary infections because of poor hygiene facilities (R17).

The specific call for a bi-hourly cleaning schedule reflects a demand for proactive and frequent maintenance to mitigate health risks. Together, these narratives position adequate, safe, and hygienic physical infrastructure as a non-negotiable foundation for student health, security, and effective academic participation.

Some participants reported uncertainty in the program, with one pointing, ".....Yeah, I have, but it is quite funny. I think that we are the first batch of this program, so all the new experiments are being applied or tried on us. That's why I am a little bit unsure about the outcomes of this program (R54).

5.0 DISCUSSION

The Administrative Processes scale emerged as the most psychometrically robust measure in the study, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82, indicating better reliability, showing that administrative interactions are reliably assessed by students, unlike more abstract constructs. In accordance with [42] findings, which suggest that access to technology and instructional resources enhances student engagement and achievement, adequate ICT facilities are listed as institutional inputs. However, the middling ratings for library resources and teaching practices, which may restrict internal efficiency, match previous concerns about resource disparities in academic institutions [43]. This pattern is consistent with more general demographic changes in teacher education, which are frequently dominated by women [44], [45], [46].

Although perceptions of policy transparency and appraisal mechanisms were slightly lower (63.1% agreement), they remained generally favourable. This aligns with HCT, which affirms that investment in teacher education enhances broader societal capability [47], [48], [49], [50]. The relationship between teaching practices and student success is aligned with [51]. The positive link between administrative services and outcomes [52] supports the role of transparent and supportive systems in fostering academic fulfillment. These relationships demonstrate that the internal efficiency of ITEP institutions is strengthened when instructional, administrative, and infrastructural inputs are well-coordinated to promote optimal student outcomes [53]. These findings also reflect established insights on teaching innovation and assessment. Innovative pedagogy and formative assessment promote deeper learning and skill acquisition, according to [14], [54], [55], [56]. However, the ongoing theory-practice divide in teacher education remains a persistent problem, as emphasized by [57], [58].

Various studies [59], [60], [61], [62] confirm that structures within an institution and administrative efficiency remain important investments in uplifting educational quality and workforce preparedness. Studies showing that administrative competence promote academic implementation [63], [64] support the effectiveness of administrative systems at ITEP institutions, which aligns with the concepts of Human Capital Theory [1], [10]. However, despite their importance, areas such as counseling and welfare services were viewed as less robust. This conclusion is consistent with [65], who found that inadequate student support systems can prevent teacher preparation programs from fully realizing internal efficiency. Together, predictors explained approximately 28.8% of the variance in student success outcomes. It is therefore consistent with past studies [60], [66] on educational efficiency and institutional effectiveness, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of student success in ITEP.

Participants provided administrative and academic interventions, stating,

"Our major teaching facility can be improved. A day should be dedicated to a doubt-clearing session, with one day allocated to each subject. Details about the Scholarship should be discussed in class. Practice materials for non-core

subjects should be provided" (R62).

Participants identified key areas for institutional improvement. One participant Faculty member emphasized the importance of “infrastructure, efficient teachers & good quality research work” (R72). Another specifically recommended “more institutional infrastructures, more AI tools, and lesser workload” (R75). This result is consistent with [67] research, which finds excessive workloads, administrative difficulties, and a lack of institutional support as major causes of teacher burnout. Reduced student enthusiasm, decreased classroom engagement, and lower overall educational achievement are just a few of the observable negative effects of burnout. Promethi goes on to say that there is great potential for reducing faculty burden through the deliberate integration of digital technologies and AI-driven automation, which are now underutilized. The study emphasizes the necessity of implementing balanced workloads and utilizing technological advancements to assist faculty and, subsequently, improve student achievement.

In the context of funding and staffing within the ITEP institutions, two management participants emphasized the necessity of stable financial and human resource allocation. One participant stated, "ITEP needs regular staff and adequate funds from the government" (MGT2), while another echoed, "Allocation of proper budget for ITEP COURSE" (MGT3).

6. CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of institutional inputs, teaching practices, assessment, and administrative processes and services on student success and human capital outcomes within Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) institutions in Punjab. Findings revealed that institutional inputs and administrative processes significantly contribute to student success, while teaching practices alone had a limited effect. Overall, the internal efficiency of ITEP depends on the alignment of institutional resources, effective administration, and integrated pedagogical practices.

7. FURTHER RESEARCH

Future research should investigate the longitudinal impacts of ITEP graduates on classroom performance and community outcomes to assess the sustained development of human capital. Conducting longitudinal designs tracking cohorts over time would strengthen causal claims regarding efficiency determinants. Additionally, comparative studies across states and program types (e.g., ITEP vs. traditional B.Ed.) could further elucidate the unique efficiency pathways of integrated teacher education models.

8. POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Policies should focus on improving the quality and availability of institutional inputs, which include; infrastructure, resources for learning purposes, and ICT, to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Strengthening administrative systems through clear decision- making, better services to student and staff ensuring Faculty are accountable. Overall, investment in institutional capacity and governance reforms is essential for achieving sustainable human capital development and improving the quality of teacher education in Punjab.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Universities should invest more in physical infrastructure, ICT, and teaching resources to improve instructional quality and learning efficiency.
2. Universities should prioritize administrative processes that are student-centered, including counseling, record management, and welfare services, to support academic success and overall well-being.
3. ITEP should strengthen the connection between pedagogical theory and teaching practice through mentorship, practicum experiences, and continuous feedback mechanisms.
4. Regular professional development should be provided to enhance innovative teaching and assessment methods that are in line with 21st-century skills.

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